

ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF COVID-19 CHALLENGES ON PSYCHOSOCIAL WELL-BEING OF NIGERIANS

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Abstract:

Assessment of the impact of COVID-19 challenges on the psychosocial wellbeing of the Nigerian populace are the focus of this paper. There are diverse reasons for the essence of assessment of this pandemic; however, the major reason is to document it for future generations. This study, therefore, examined the challenges faced by the populace as a result of COVID-19 pandemic in the South-Western zone and Nigeria as a whole. The study was conducted using a volunteering sampling technique and 335 participants were used using telephone inquiry. Those who completed the interview were 203 (60.6%) males and the rest 132 (39.4%) were female respondents. The instrument has a reliability coefficient of 0.76. Some of the challenges or impacts of COVID-19 on Nigeria populace are hunger, lawlessness, arm robbery, economic crisis, political crisis, financial problem, and hike in the price of essential commodities, young adults resulting in abuse of drugs, raping, pool betting, and internet fraudsters. The spiritual houses like churches, mosques, and shrine were closed up, couples that have given up raising child still found themselves in it as a result of lockdown order and finally the loss of love ones due to CORONA Virus. Based on these findings it was concluded that COVID-19 among the citizenry had cost Nigerians a lot of havoc.

Keywords: assessment, impact, COVID-19, challenges, psychosocial, well-being

1. Introduction

The Covid-19 is a [pandemic](#) of [corona-virus](#) symptomized with the [severe acute respiratory syndrome, dry cough, difficulty breathing, persistent chest pain or pressure, sudden confusion, difficulty walking, and bluish face or lips body temperature, severe headache, and the complications may include pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome](#). According to (China-WHO, 2020) the outbreak was identified in [Wuhan](#),

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China, in December 2019. The [World Health Organization](#) declared the outbreak to be a [Public Health Emergency of International Concern](#) on 30 January 2020, and then recognized it as a pandemic on 11 March 2020. As of 18 April 2020, [more than 2.25 million cases](#) of COVID-19 have been reported in [210 countries and territories](#), resulting in [more than 154,000 deaths](#). More than 571,000 people have recovered. Further, WHO (2019) noted that the development of the disease can lead to severe [pneumonia](#), [acute respiratory distress syndrome](#), [sepsis](#), [septic shock](#), and death. Some of those infected maybe asymptomatic, with no clinical symptoms but test results that confirm infection, so researchers have issued advice that those with close contact to confirmed infected people should be closely monitored and examined to rule out infection (Zho, Lin, Ran, Musa, Yang, Wang, 2020).

According to (Zhao, Zhuang, Ran, Lin, Yang & Yan, 2020) the virus is primarily [spread](#) between people during close contact, often via [small droplets](#) produced by coughing, sneezing, or talking. While these droplets are produced when breathing out, they usually fall to the ground or onto surfaces rather than [being infectious over long distances](#). Wang and Zhang (2020); Wu, Zhao, Yu, Chen, et al (2020) said people may also become infected by touching a contaminated surface and then touching their eyes, nose, or mouth. The virus can survive on surfaces for up to 72 hours. It is most contagious during the first three days after the onset of symptoms, although spread may be possible before symptoms appear and in later stages of the disease. The [time from exposure to onset of symptoms](#) is typically around five days but may range from two to fourteen days. There is [no known vaccine](#) or [specific antiviral treatment](#) for now. The primary treatment is [symptomatic](#) and [supportive therapy](#) (Chen, Rui, Wang, Zhao, Cui & Yin, 2020).

Recommended [preventive measures](#) include [hand washing](#), covering one's mouth when coughing, [maintaining distance from other people](#), and monitoring and [self-isolation](#) for people who suspect they are infected. Authorities worldwide have [responded](#) by implementing [travel restrictions](#), [quarantines](#), [curfews and stay-at-home orders](#), [workplace hazard controls](#), and [facility closures](#). Face masks have also been recommended for use by those taking care of someone who may have the disease. The WHO (2020) has recommended healthy people wear masks only if they are at high risks, such as those who are caring for a person with COVID-19. China and the United States, among other countries, have encouraged the use of face masks or cloth face coverings more generally by members of the public to limit the spread of the virus by asymptomatic individuals. Several national and local governments have made wearing masks mandatory. Varying recommendations for wearing masks have been a subject of debate.

Thompson (2020) discovered that development is the result of society's capacity to organize resources to meet challenges and opportunities. Society passes through well-defined stages in the course of its development. They are [nomadic hunting and gathering](#), [rural agrarian](#), [urban](#), commercial, industrial, and [post-industrial](#) societies. Pioneers introduce new ideas, practices, and habits that conservative elements initially resist. At a later stage, innovations are accepted, imitated, organized, and used by other members of the community.

Wilder-Smith & Freedman (2020) claimed that organizational improvements introduced to support the innovations can take place simultaneously at four different levels—physical, social, mental, and psychological. Moreover, four different types of resources are involved in promoting development. Of these four, physical resources are most visible, but least capable of expansion. The productivity of resources increases enormously as the quality of organization and level of knowledge inputs rise.

Theories of psychosocial well-being (PWB) generally, focus on understanding the *structure* of psychological wellbeing or the *dynamics* (i.e. the causes and consequences of PWB). The breakdown of psychological wellbeing into hedonic and eudemonics components and Carol Ryff's model have widely accepted theories of the structure of PWB.

As far as the dynamics of PWB are concerned it's important to recognize that, to some extent, PWB is relatively stable and will have been influenced by both previous experience (including, for example, early upbringing) and underlying personality. Stressful experiences can predispose people to subsequent mood and anxiety disorders (Sullivan, Strickland & Howard, 2020); but, on the other hand, exposure to extremely traumatic events can help to build resilience and actually protect PWB. For children exposed to moderately stressful events seem better able to cope with subsequent stressors (Daszak & Drosten, 2020). The same "inoculating" impact of stressful events has also been observed in working adults (Gilbert, Poletto & Belle, et al. 2020).

Although baseline psychological wellbeing may be fairly stable, day to day events and experiences also exert an impact. For example, even the most resilient person may eventually become very low, or depressed, if his or her daily experiences are constantly troubling. There is strong evidence to show that exposure to work-related stressors over long periods of time will have a negative impact on PWB, so, although as mentioned above, short periods of adversity may be helpful in building resilience, long-term stress is not good for PWB. In turn, this lower level of PWB may well lead to serious illness, including cardiovascular disease, problems with blood sugar control, such as diabetes and immune system malfunctions (Calisher, Carroll et al., 2020).

PWB theory proposes that early experience and underlying personality create a platform for PWB but everyday experiences can help to maintain a good level of PWB (if they are positive) or, if they are negative, reduce levels of PWB, leading, in turn, to poor health outcomes. Studies have discovered that people with higher psychological well-being are more likely to live healthier and longer lives. They are also more likely to enjoy a better quality of life. Better psychological well-being also is associated with fewer social problems. For instance, research has found that people with high psychological well-being are less likely to engage in criminal activity or abuse drugs and alcohol. In addition, positive psychological well-being tends to predict higher earnings and more [pro-social behaviour](#), such as volunteering. This is the principle of PWB which this study wants to see how the COVID-19 pandemic has in the life of Southwest, Nigeria populace.

The problem of CORONA Virus started suddenly from a far country (China) to Nigeria as an epidemic. All of a sudden it spread to many Asia countries, Europe and finally to Africa and all other continents of the world. Therefore, the researcher is

interested in study the impact of it on Nigeria populace on how it affects social life, their economics, governance, health facilities, breakdown of law and orders, death of loved ones, the effect of it on industries, etc. The idea behind it is to be able to plan ahead of the future occurrence of such natural disasters. Hence, the purpose of this study is to assess the impact of COVID-19 challenges on the psychosocial well-being of Nigeria citizenry.

1.1 Participants

All households in South West, Nigeria, with a telephone connected and the telephone number of friends and families were eligible for selection in the sample. Telephone numbers were selected randomly from the researcher's phone contacts. There were no replacements for non-contactable persons. A sample of 405 was drawn of which 335 participants responded were made used, losses occurred due to network problems by not hearing the participants well. From the eligible sample of 335, completed interviews were conducted with 203 persons (60.6%) were male and the rest 132 (39.4%) were female.

1.2 Measures

Respondents provided information about their experience during this COVID-19 and how it affects their psychological well-being was measured using the research the instrument by the researcher on the Impacts of COVID-19 on Psychological Wellbeing of Nigerians Populace comprising five items which require the respondent to indicate to what extent they agree or disagree with the statement on a four point Likert type scale with higher scores corresponding to a higher life satisfaction. The instrument has about 8 different sections. These subscales were chosen to reflect the impacts of COVID-19 on hunger, arm robbery, economic, political, and financial and spiritual problems, hospital facilities, mental health depression, traditional alternative herbal medicine for COVID-19 treatment, religion, cancelation of ceremony and social gathering, lockdown effect on youths, adolescents and married couples and the supportive social relationships and how it enhances poverty which has been consistently identified as integral aspects of psychological wellbeing. The instrument was the trial-tested for factor analysis, reliability, and validity analysis and it was found to have a validity coefficient of 0.76.

1.3 Procedure

In carrying out this survey study the researcher introduced himself to the individual participants of each selected telephone number. The researcher informed people of the purpose of the survey and indicated that they could expect a telephone call within a defined time frame. Before the conduct of the main survey, the questionnaire was pilot tested (n = 50), and where appropriate, the wording was amended slightly.

2. Results

The outcomes of the findings are discussed below.

Research Question: What are the impacts of COVID-19 as perceived by the respondents in their areas of living?

This research question was answered using frequency counts with the data obtained from the respondents.

Table 1: Frequency Counts on Impacts of COVID-19
on Psychological Well-being of the Respondents in their place of living

The following are the impacts of COVID-19 in the area that I am living/staying	Agree	Disagree
COVID-19 made people to get hungry	251 (70.6%)	104 (29.4%)
It promotes arm robbery	298 (83.9%)	57 (16.1%)
It worsens the economic situation in the country	250 (70.5%)	105 (49.5%)
It affects the political situation in the country	261 (73.4%)	94 (26.6%)
It leads to financial difficulty	219 (61.7%)	136 (38.3%)
It leads to spirituality problems	297 (83.7%)	58 (16.3%)
It shows that Nigeria hospitals lack treatment facilities	346 (97.4%)	9 (2.6%)
Lockdown order leads to mental health depression	333 (93.9%)	22 (6.1%)
People results in traditional alternative herbal medicine for COVID-19 treatment	329 (92.8%)	26 (7.2%)
It leads to the cancelation of ceremony and social gathering	194 (54.6%)	161 (45.4%)
Lockdown order have a negative effect on youths, adolescents and married couples leading to an unexpected pregnancy	212 (59.6%)	143 (40.4%)
COVID-19 made us to know that we need to support one another socially	320 (90%)	35 (10%)
COVID-19 enhances/creates poverty	316 (89%)	39 (11%)
Religion activities were paralyzed in the nation as going to Churches, Mosques, and shrines was completely prevented	207 (58.2%)	148 (41.8%)
It leads to the death of loved ones	215 (60.7%)	140 (39.3%)
It leads to closure of the school at all levels	203 (57.1%)	152 (42.8%)
Hike in the price of essential commodities	185 (52.1%)	170 (47.9%)

It was discovered that the following among others were the impacts of COVID-19 on the psychosocial well-being of Nigeria as shown in the above table: hunger, arm robbery, economic, political, and financial and spiritual problems, hospital facilities, death of loved ones, closure of schools at all levels, mental health depression, traditional alternative herbal medicine for COVID-19 treatment, religion, production industries have to stop, hike in the price of essential commodities, Cancelation of various programs and

social gathering, lockdown effect on youths, adolescents and married couples and the supportive social relationships and how it enhances poverty which has been consistently identified as integral aspects of psychological wellbeing. All the above mentioned factors are the impacts or challenges of COVID-19 on Nigeria populace.

3. Discussion

Poverty is a state or condition in which a person or community lacks the financial resources and essentials for a minimum standard of living. Poverty means that the income level from employment is so low that basic human needs cannot be met. When we think about poverty, we usually think about economics. In reality, poverty has a face. COVID-19 actually showcases the level of poverty in the country in the sense that as a result of lockdown many parents could not afford food for the children. A mother said it openly; *‘I am looking for someone who is interested in having fun with me for a token of five hundred nairas for her to get money to feed her children’*. She said she cannot open her eyes seeing her children dying of hunger and that there is no one who is ready to borrow or give her money to take care of her children. The poverty was in existence but that of COVID-19 experience was more severe. Many could not eat three meals a day. Many embark on food in the morning, nothing in the afternoon, and food in the evening. Many embark on the afternoon alone or evening alone. Within two weeks of lockdown, many have died of starvation and many respondents said the number of people that died of starvation is more than those who died of starvation. So many parents cannot afford to buy drugs for themselves and their children. Many media houses were broadcasting day-in-day-out that masses are hungry, and they are looking for philanthropists that could assist them to get food to eat and many could have resulted in begging if not because of lockdown. Many became night maunders going to people’s houses to forcefully carry their belongings like foods, money, and some other things that can be easily sold and get money to buy food. Many people looked haggard and thin going about with hunger.

Fehintola (2018) define disease as a state of physiological and morphological disorder in plants and animals. The disease is literally the absence of ease or elbow room. The basic idea is of an impediment to free movement. Illness has three definitions. Two of them are of the way the word was used *“unpleasantness, disagreeableness, hurtfulness”*. The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted or gave birth to some other diseases numerous to mention. Many diseases that could be contacted when one could not get food to eat. Some of these diseases to mention but few are thin look, abdominal pain, exposure of ribs, malnutrition, kwashiorkor, and the kind of diseases except adequate feeding. This issue of disease is one of the burnouts of the COVID-19 disease lockdown measure and it seriously affecting the general wellbeing of masses(Wu, Chen & Chan, 2019).

Lawlessness, hardly a day passes which does not show us the effects of lawlessness in our society and how it has changed “normal life.” The effects range from mere “inconveniences” to jeopardizing one’s financial or physical safety. We are not talking about the normal dangers of life parse – human beings have lived with danger and mishaps to varying degrees all down through the years. However, the degree of

lawlessness nowadays is higher due to COVID-19 lockdown every landlord have become night guards in order to secure the lives of their families and their properties from lawlessness people that are looking for means of surviving at all cost. Some individuals dared the security agents in order to get their daily needs by going out when they are not supposed to go out. The security agents beat some arrested some yet that does not prevent people from violating the rules of not going out. The lawlessness during the COVID-19 pandemic is so high to the extent that when young children are hawking food items some would such child to a corridor and forcefully collect such items and ran away. Things have changed. Our lives have become worst in many ways, but the effects of increasing lawlessness impact our daily lives in ways large and small. During this COVID-19 pandemic, one could see people smoking hard drugs openly and after said and done so many crimes acts will follow like raping, stabbing and robbing people of their possession in the daylight.

Africa's leading economy, Nigeria has a population of nearly 200 million people. Worldwide, it is the 30th largest economy, by GDP volume. However, Nigeria's economy is highly dependent on oil and is therefore very vulnerable to fluctuations in crude oil prices and production. In 2020, the price of crude oil falls below expectations making the federal government reduce its annual budget. Many industries locally have folded up due to lock down and these industries could not afford to pay the salary of their staffers. The commodities that these industries have produced before COVID-19 have increased in price, all these are the burnout of COVID-19 and it goes a long way to affects the wellbeing of masses.

Social services in the southwest, Nigeria, had been withdrawn as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Sovereignty is not a right; it is a responsibility, in political terms it is the responsibility of the state to deliver education, health care, infrastructure, public services, good governance, and protection from violence and crime among others. However, since the inception of the COVID-19 pandemic, all these social services had become a mirage. The government has closed down schools from primary school level to university level, the health care services presently during this pandemic is mainly for the victims of COVID-19. Nobody is willing to go to the hospital, since the health care provider is also falling a victim of COVID-19 due to lack of proper and adequate security in terms of safety from the contagious disease of COVID-19.

Religious affiliation in Nigeria is strongly related to ethnicity, with rather distinct regional divisions between ethnic groups. The northern states, dominated by the Hausa and Fulani groups, are predominantly Muslim while the southern ethnic groups have a large number of Christians. In the southwest, there is no predominant religion. The Yoruba tribe, which is the majority ethnic group in the southwest, practices Christianity, Muslim, and/or the traditional Yoruba religion, which centers on the belief in one supreme god and several lesser deities. Overall statistics indicate that about 50% of the population is Muslim. About 40% are Christian and about 10% practice traditional African religions or no religion at all. Many people include elements of traditional beliefs in their own practice of Christianity or Islam. These people cannot but go to churches, mosques, and grooves to worship their God and gods respectively. But since the

inception of COVID-19, these have seized to go to their place of worship for fear of contacting the CORONA virus. All churches, mosques, and traditional worship centers had been closed down (JPCMSC, 2020).

Hospital Facilities, the evolution of the Covid-19 pandemic has actually thrown open that in Nigeria we only have structure/building called hospital without any equipment therein. It was clearly and openly said that if one is not seriously sick one should not go to the hospital except one is looking for trouble. The pandemic of Covid-19 made us as Nigerians to know that ordinary glove, syringe, needle, and some simple tablets are not even available in some of our so-called Federal Medical centers. Some hospitals cannot boast of life support garget (ventilator). These scenarios led to the death of many medical practitioners and some of them absconded from duty due to lack of equipment to combat the CORONA Virus (GAQS, 2016).

On palliative measures, the philanthropists made some donations, and the people that are to share the cushioning commodities ended up sharing the money and the food items donated among themselves and their relatives. The only palliative experience by the civil populace is beating and collecting bribe from innocent people who could not stay at home because of hunger. The security agents beat the hell out some people because of not following the order to stay at home and stay safe. And people who could afford to give money to security people may be allowed to go Scott free without being tortured.

All most all the citizens are entertaining fear of one thing or the others. The fear of contacting COVID-19 is the major source of fear for the populace since there are no adequate medical facilities for treatment. Some citizens are afraid of death due to cremation of the corpse of COVID-19 victims. Majority of people who have aged parents who are thinking that as a child he/she suppose to bury their parents by given them befitting burial ceremony are now thinking that they may not be able to do so either as a result that they died before their parents due to COVID-19 or if their parents died during this pandemic they may not be allowed to give such befitting burial to their parents. During this pandemic, there is the fear of night marauders who visited households in the night to collect money, foodstuff, and some other valuable things. The aged and the young adults who are suffering from one ailment or the other are afraid and could not visit health facilities for fear of being contacted COVID-19. These set of people are afraid of falling dead and more so that there was information that people who always fall prey to COVID-19 are people who have one ailment or the other. Many pregnant women could not access the health facilities since the majority of primary health facilities are closed up due to fear of contracting the pandemic. Also, the secondary health facilities in the nation are focused on COVID-19, despite the fact that there are no adequate facilities to combat COVID-19. Furthermore, the psychological wellbeing of the civil populace is affected as results of COVID-19 because of fear of losing their job and some have been subjected to half salary due to lockdown syndrome. Also, fear gripped many people on the basis that the worship centers like churches, mosques, and shrines are closed up and these are the places where many go to get relieved to their problems. And as a result of this many have taken to drugs as an alternative means to get relieved and some have even died.

NCDC (2020) said there should not be any social gathering of any kind and due to this instruction, there were many cancellations of social events like burial, wedding, birthday, naming, house warming, convocation ceremony and the likes due to COVID-19 are quite enormous. The University of Lagos has canceled her annual convocation ceremonies, previously scheduled for March 2020, due to the COVID-19 outbreak. Many would-be couples that have printed and circulate wedding invitation later announced the cancellation of their wedding ceremony citing the COVID-19 pandemic and the directives from the federal and state governments regarding social distancing and lockdown. Many burial ceremonies scheduled for March - June 2020's were canceled. Because people will not be able to attend a funeral ceremony, according to the announcement made on social media, television stations, and radio stations, and even in the notice boards of churches and mosques, but are advised to check back for any alternative plans made. "This was a difficult decision," read a statement on the notice boards of Churches, mosques, and hearing it over air and Church's website. *"It is clear that it would have been impossible to hold such large gatherings in person."* Birthday and many social gathering were canceled due to social distancing, several large gatherings; for example, involved 27 ceremonies over 17 days for 14,000 marriage notification, plus their guests. Graduates will receive their degrees and will be mailed their parchments, the legal document embossed with the university seal, and the graduate's name and degree after the degrees have been conferred. "We appreciate that the cancellation of the academic conference will come as a huge disappointment to our conferees, the local organizing committee, the sellers of one commodity and others," reads the statement on Websites of Conference organizers.

Overall, consumers are dramatically reducing the most unnecessary spending, which has grave consequences for some industries, such as restaurants, apparel, footwear, accessories, travel, and entertainment out of the home. As many consumers are under stay-at-home or shelter-in-place orders around the nation. Many of the hoteliers were heard complaining of low patronage more so that people are under lockdown orders. The purchasing habits before and during the COVID-19 peak indicate that spending in a number of categories remains low for the first two months of March and April and this pattern may linger after COVID-19 pending the time when people economics become buoyancy. Consumer behavior has changed in terms of stockpiling. Many households did not store food and household items in an amount necessary to overcome even short supply shortages. Because of the sudden occurrence of COVID-19 in Nigeria and sudden lockdown order in the country did not allow the consumer to make bulk buying. The few consumers who are buoyant only spent their money on staples such as food, household supplies, and personal care items, and the poor ones embark on few things they could afford to buy due to an increase in the price of staple foods or carbohydrate foods in general. The price of common foods that are easily accessible to common masses has gone up by 100 percent. Most especially staple foods like gari, yam flour, yam tuber, and vegetables despite the fact people don't have money to buy these foodstuffs.

Corruptions in high places, the money donated by philanthropists that supposed to be given to the poor masses were not given to them. It was hanging in the hand of top government functionary officers. This attitude adds more to the suffering of the poor masses who are living from hand to mouth and this makes the lockdown order not be effective as expected. Because some people preferred to die of COVID-19 that been killed by hunger when they know that when they out there they can get something to eat. The majority of poor masses prefer to go out and beg their neighbour for food or do the menial jobs to get some things to eat. The little palliative given by both Federal and state government was given to the people that are actually in need of palliative.

Lockdown effects on youths, adolescents, and married couples, many youths and adolescents have committed serious errors for life which cannot be reversed. Because the majority of them have turned the stay at home and stay safe into sexual immorality. Some of the youths have put daughters of their neighbour into family ways. While some of them have committed incest and they have put themselves into family ways as results of lockdown order due to COVID-19. Some couples that are no longer expecting a baby(ies) any more are expectant mothers and fathers due to lockdown orders. Married individuals who have stopped procreation are back into it, many of them thought staying at home order given by the government is for them to be having sexual intercourse and this act has resulted in unexpected pregnancy of baby/babies. In essence, by this time next year 2021, the results of the lockdown order will result in having newborn babies that will lead to population explosion. The majority of the young adults have turned to be drug addicts ranging from smoking marijuana, heroin, cocaine, snuffing some tablets, and a mixture of one drug or the others together as a result of lockdown order. While some of them have resulted to pool betting and gambling both physically and online. It is true that an idle hand is the devil workshop, due to COVID-19 pandemic Nigeria future leaders have turned to devil's workshop.

Necessity, they say is the mother of invention, when the government, medical practitioners, and hospital facilities had failed everybody people then resulted in alternative therapy known as a traditional herbal medicine for the treatment of COVID-19 and for other ailments because the hospital has failed to perform their duty. COVID-19 has taught us a lot on herbal medicine people did say that *"Ginger, Garlic, Turmeric, Onion and Lemon that have been with us for ages and for other uses have suddenly found use in the management of COVID-19 as attested by the many people it means that our herbs hold great future if we harnessed item fully and thoroughly and we have been on this realization for long God bless us"*. This and many other statements are attested to by the masses due to COVID-19 pandemic lockdown and failure of the government, hospital facilities, and health caregivers (Fehintola, 2013 and JPCMSC, 2020).

4. Conclusion

The researcher concludes that all the challenges discussed in this paper-like, famine, poverty, wretchedness, sickness, destruction, lawlessness, arm robbery, social maladjustment, economic melt-down, financial problem, an unexpected pregnancy,

abuse of drugs, hike in the price of commodities, political problem, mental health distress, and spiritual problem that people are exposed to are as a result of lockdown which is a burn out of COVID-19.

4.1 Recommendations

- **Personal Hygiene** – As deadly as Coronavirus is, practicing personal hygiene like washing your hands regularly and using hand sanitizer has proven to be effective against its spread. At any business locations, we should continue to provide ourselves with hand sanitizers or soap and water to wash our hands. Use the hand sanitizers provided to ourselves or water and soap to thoroughly wash our hands for 20 seconds before and after touching any objects.
- **Face Masks to Keep You Safe** – For your safety and that of others, wearing face masks should be enforced at all outings. The security personnel should work with the masses to ensure compliance nationwide.
- **Hand Gloves for your Safety** – The government should insist that everybody wear hand gloves before gaining access to public places nationwide. The security personnel should work with the civil populace to ensure compliance with wearing hand gloves when going out of their place.
- **Social Distancing** – It is important for an individual to allow space between him/herself and the next person to stay safe. This is because social distancing stops the spread of COVID-19. We should, therefore, implemented social distancing protocols in all our social engagement and premises. Social distance parameters should be clearly marked at our premises. When on the queue at the markets and malls social distance should be observed.
- **Adhering to Safety Protocols** – Our security personnel should be on the ground to ensure that we adhere to all safety precautions necessary to keep us and other people safe and ultimately flatten the curve. People should please listen to them and follow the advice of security people.

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